

www.bjisrd.com

Pedagogical and Psychological Classification of Hadiths Based on Imam Al-Buhari's Work "Al-Adab Al Mufrad."

Saidnazarova Gulshan Bolta kizi,

Teacher of the Department of Pedagogy of Bukhara State University

***Abstract:** In the article, the scientific activity of Imam Ismail al-Bukhari, the study of his works, including "Al-Jame-as-Sahih" and "Al-adab-al mufrad," the interpretation of the content of the hadiths about spiritual and moral education in them. The upbringing of children in the family is considered an important issue, and the hadiths widely cover issues related to the duty of parents to the child and the duty of the child to the parents.*

***Key words:** Etiquette, hadith, education, muhaddith, sahih, personal qualities, politeness, kindness, al-Jame' as-sahih, al-Adab al-mufrad, greeting etiquette.*

Introduction.

Based on scientific standards of the concepts provided in hadiths, which are regarded as the rich spiritual legacy of great thinkers, a plethora of scientific research institutes and centers throughout the globe are undertaking in-depth study on the substance of hadiths. The VIII International Congress "The Heritage of Great Ancestors - the Foundation of the Third Renaissance" was recently held in Tashkent and Samarkand from August 23 to 26. The purpose of this congress was to promote New Uzbekistan's development path in the cultural and humanitarian sphere, the achievements of the new era of progress, and reforms in religious education, as well as to study and preserve the rich cultural and spiritual heritage of our people. To guarantee successful collaboration with regional scientists and the global scientific expert community, a significant event was planned. 35 different nations sent scientists to the meeting. The attendees became acquainted with the current Imam al-Bukhari complex building. They also went to the School of Hadith Science and the Imam al-Bukhari Research Center. In these difficult times, the scientific community is particularly focused on thoroughly investigating the significance of Imam Bukhari's hadiths for promoting sustainable development.

Hadiths continue to be important for moral education, thought cultivation, and thought change, even in this time of spiritual and ideological conflict. Truly, the teachings of Imam Ismail al-Bukhari are

profoundly meaningful, not only pedagogically but also psychologically. Through this hadith, it is appropriate to study how to raise a child with kindness, humility, sincerity, and love for children, while also fostering their personal qualities, self-love and love for others, self-confidence, and positive manifestation of emotional-volitional qualities. The following hadith can be used to further investigate this: Ya'lo ibn Murra (r.a.) related: We went to a place where we were invited after leaving the Prophet's (peace be upon him) residence. Husayn was playing on the street, as we could see. The Prophet (peace be upon him) hurriedly stepped in front of the crowd and then extended his hands in their direction. The Prophet (peace be upon him) chuckled as he pursued the youngster, who laughed too. At last, he grasped him and caressed him with one hand under his chin and the other on his head before giving him an embrace.

Then he said, "Husayn is from me (that is, my grandson), and I am from Husayn (his grandfather). Allah loves those who love Husayn. Husayn is one of the grandchildren." Therefore, when a person loves their child or grandchild and respects them as an individual by patting their head, it increases the child's self-confidence for the future. The fact that embracing and showing affection to children has a positive impact on their upbringing is also proven in modern psychology.

Research Methodology

Through in-depth study of hadiths and their application in practice, one can reach such breadth and depth of human spirituality that it becomes very easy to influence and educate from this perspective. Although hadiths have been studied from artistic-literary, historical, and pedagogical aspects, their psychological aspects have not received attention. However, hadiths are interconnected with the science of psychology in studying the human psyche, worldview, thinking, and other character traits to understand their essence and influence them. Currently, the psychological aspects of hadiths are being widely studied in the process of education and upbringing. In particular, the content of Imam Ismail al-Bukhari's works "Al-jami' as-sahih" and "Al-adab al-mufrad" are being studied by domestic and foreign scholars.

Analysis and results.

The hadiths reflect the human qualities required for human perfection, such as showing kindness, generosity, openness, care for parents and elders, relatives, respect, mercy to the poor, love for the homeland, praise of labor and profession, honesty, purity, mutual friendship, peacefulness, and others.

Raising a child in the family is considered an important issue, and the hadiths widely cover topics such as giving birth to a child, giving them a beautiful name, raising them, and the duties of parents towards children and children towards parents. We can cite the following as an example.

Aisha (r.a.) narrates: "A Bedouin came to the Prophet (peace be upon him) and said, 'Do you kiss your young children? We do not kiss them.' The Prophet (peace be upon him) said, 'What can I do if Allah has removed mercy from your heart?'" This hadith implies that children should be loved, kissed, cherished, given affection, cared for, and communicated with well. For parents to raise a child as a well-rounded person in the future, they must first be able to set an example, love, and understand. Modern psychology also emphasizes the health benefits of kissing and caressing a child. Kissing a child on the forehead brings positive changes to their health. It increases their self-confidence. Indeed, children are the ones who need love and compassion. Because if they do not receive love from adults at a young age, expecting love from them when they grow up is like expecting fruit from a tree that has been planted. One of the pressing problems today is that due to parents' indifference to their children and neglect of their upbringing, children are increasingly developing negative traits such as

nervousness, irritability, and lack of discipline. Our hadiths serve as an important resource for preventing these situations. In hadiths, bad habits and actions are condemned as sins, while good and virtuous actions and activities for human well-being and societal prosperity are praised as merits.

Accordingly, it is emphasized that eating the property of orphans, coveting wealth, lying, gossiping, slandering, committing adultery, engaging in drunkenness, drug abuse, excessive idle talk, and other vices are considered sins. On the other hand, caring for parents, the elderly, the weak, and the needy, visiting them, remembering the deceased with kind words, and not betraying trusts are counted as good deeds.

A person's perfection is directly linked to their health. After all, only a healthy person can actively contribute to the well-being of both family and society. In Hadiths and Islamic teachings in general, great attention is paid to cleanliness and purity, including spiritual and physical purity: "The True God is pure and loves purity, He is clean and loves cleanliness, He is of supreme generosity and loves those with high aspirations, He is open-hearted and loves open-heartedness."

By paying attention to, getting to know, observing, committing to memory, comprehending the material, and examining Hadiths, we are able to implement their lessons in our everyday routine. This aids us in rectifying deficiencies in our personality and upbringing.

The hadiths express the human qualities required for a person to achieve perfection. Among these qualities, it is important to show kindness to others, be generous, open-hearted, honor and respect parents, always seek blessings from our parents, pray for them, care for them, be able to make them proud of us when appropriate, always brighten their faces, hold their heads high because of us, always show proper respect, be kind to elders and relatives, show them affection, respect them, take care of them, and be respectful to elders while being courteous to the young. Such qualities as love for one's homeland, glorification of work and profession, honesty, purity, friendship, nobility, compassion, humility, truthfulness, and conscientiousness are included. Additionally, the teachings that a person should refrain from evil deeds and strive for goodness are also reflected. All of these are based on the instructions recorded in the Holy Qur'an and serve as the main criteria for the formation of a perfect person. The hadiths, in terms of content, strengthen the beliefs and convictions of every believer while calling a person to spiritual perfection. Another helpful source for each of us to develop these qualities in ourselves, and one of the sources of education, is the practical application of these hadiths. Among the hadiths, the theme of kinship and maintaining family ties was considered relevant. In particular, Abul Fadl Ziyad ibn Muhammad, who lived in Samarkand, narrated a hadith that says: "Whoever guarantees me one thing, I guarantee him four things: [2] If he maintains family ties (holds fast to kinship), his family will love him, his sustenance will be abundant, his life will be long, and Allah will admit him into the Paradise He promised." Hadiths on doing good to parents and not displeasing.

Conclusions and Recommendations.

In conclusion, it can be said that the hadiths in Imam Ismail al-Bukhari's work "Al-adab al-Mufrad" help to form the following qualities in a person, which primarily serve to develop the attributes of perfection:

- self-awareness;
- purity of faith;
- vigilance of conscience;
- firmness of conviction;

- purity of heart;
- spiritual perfection;
- strengthening of will;
- tolerance;
- self-confidence;
- respect for society;
- cultivation of high moral qualities, etc.

Indeed, as Professor Sh. Olimov emphasizes in his monograph "Fundamentals of Spiritual and Moral Education," "Spirituality is a complex of philosophical, legal, scientific, artistic, moral, and religious ideas and concepts of people, which are closely related to the notions of ideology and thinking, and they necessitate one another." We should not forget that the essence of human spirituality is a holistic system of intellectual, moral, scientific-practical, and ideological qualities that are inextricably linked to each other. Morality, being one of the forms of social consciousness, shapes in young people such qualities as honesty, purity, sense of duty, conscience, nobility, and selflessness.

In summary, the teachings and thoughts mentioned above underscore the significance of the educational heritage left by Imam Ismail al-Bukhari as a crucial foundation for the moral and intellectual growth of the youth.

References

1. Musayeva N.M. "Socio-anthropological issues in Imam Bukhari's work 'Al-Jami as-Sahih' (Philosophical analysis) " Doctor of Philosophy (DSc) dissertation abstract
2. Sheikh Muhammad Sodiq Muhammad Yusuf "Treasury of Manners" "Hilol-Nashr" Tashkent 2021 p. 68
3. Hadith Studies "Lecture Text" by D. Rahimjonov, D. Muratov. 2010
4. Juraev B. The Emergence and Development of Pedagogical Activity in the East // Current Problems of Social and Humanitarian Sciences / Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences. - 2023. - Vol. 3. - No. S/2. - pp. 343-350. - C. 343-350.
5. Saidnazarova G. B. Skills of Pedagogical Influence // Bulletin of the Master's Degree. - 2019. - No. 4-3 (91). - pp. 80-81. - C. 80-81.
6. Khodjaev B., Juraev B., Amonov M. Forming the spirituality of students and youth through pilgrimage tourism // E3S Web of Conferences. - EDP Sciences, 2023. - Vol. 420. - p. 10017.
7. Saidnazarova G. STUDYING AL-BUKHARI'S SPIRITUAL AND MORAL VIEWS AS A PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM //Current Problems of Social and Humanitarian Sciences/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences. - 2023. - Vol. 3. - No. S/8. S/8.
8. Musayeva N.M. "Socio-anthropological issues in Imam Bukhari's work 'Al-Jami as-Sahih' (Philosophical analysis) " Doctor of Philosophy (DSc) dissertation abstract
9. Olimov Sh.Sh. The Foundations of Spiritual and Moral Education. Monograph. -T.: Science and Technology, 2015, - 228 p.
10. <https://www.sammuslim.uz/uz/articles/actual/zamonaviy-hadis-talimi>